

RELATIONSHIP MARKETING IN CUSTOMER LOYALTY: A CASE STUDY IN A PHARMACY NETWORK IN THE MUNICIPALITY OF ALAGOINHAS-BAHIA

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Abstract: In an increasingly competitive scenario, where the consumer has more and more options, companies have to set up and implement strategies to demonstrate their differential in front of their competitors, so that in this way they can remain competitive in their market and, thus manage to retain and attract customers. Based on this, the generating problem of the present study was “how to build and maintain lasting relationships with customers in a pharmacy?”. The general objective of this article was to verify the actions and reflections of relationship marketing in a pharmacy, having as specific objectives: to identify the profile of the clients and their buying process, to verify the forms of interaction between the company and its clients. This research is relevant to society, science and especially to the market, as the latter is increasingly competitive and has increasingly demanding customers, it is extremely important for companies to invest in strategies that differentiate them. The present study is characterized as a case study, which was carried out in the commercial area of a chain of pharmacies located in the city of Alagoinhas, in the interior of the State of Bahia and which has existed for more than 3 decades in the region . It was found that the pharmacy network studied has been efficiently applying the marketing strategies adopted by it, thus obtaining satisfactory results and managing to consolidate its brand. It is concluded that sales grew satisfactorily, relying

mainly on digital media, increasingly strengthening commercial ties with active customers and prospecting and trying to retain potential customers.

Keywords: Marketing of relationship. Loyalty. Client.

INTRODUCTION

Faced with increasing competition, consumers have seen an increase in the range of services and products offered by companies day by day. These companies, with the advance of the globalization process, have invested in the implementation of strategies to show their differentiation from competitors, so that they can remain competitive in the market, in order to achieve loyalty and attract customers. Often, these strategies are extracted from existing tools, such as those applied in the Marketing area (COBRA, 1997, 2012).

In this environment, relationship marketing emerges as a means to manage the company-customer relationship in a lasting way, so that both the company and its customers achieve expressive results. In addition, the knowledge of its importance provides the company with a differential in relation to competing companies, thus gaining the loyalty of its customers and through this, also gaining an excellent channel for publicizing its brand through the differential offered by it, in their products and services and, with that, absorb new customers in the market (GORDON, 2002).

However, there are still companies that have not realized that two important factors to acquire competitive advantage are the relationship with their customers and their loyalty through differentiated service, thus satisfying their needs. Based on this, the generating problem of the present study was to know how to build and maintain lasting relationships with customers in a pharmacy?

Faced with this need, Relationship Marketing has been gaining prominence. The objectives of Relationship Marketing are to recover, maintain and attract customers to the company, that is, currently companies are not only concerned with selling their products or services, increasing their profits, but with working in a way that they can offer their customers a high level of satisfaction, consequently to its business partners and, thus, making them become a channel of company disclosure, thus attracting new customers.

The general objective of this article was to verify the actions and reflections of Relationship Marketing in a chain of pharmacies, having as specific objectives: (a) to identify

the profile of the clients and their buying process and (b) to verify the ways of interaction between the company and its customers.

RELATIONSHIP MARKETING AND CUSTOMER RELATIONSHIP MANAGEMENT (CRM)

Relationship Marketing can be confused with the very definition of marketing, constituting an integration of efforts by companies with the purpose of identifying, building, maintaining and improving individual relationships with customers, in a process of exchanging benefits directed towards the long term. (D'ANGELO, SCHNEIDER and LARAN, 2006).

Feijó (2012) points out that relationship marketing refers to all marketing activities aimed at establishing, developing and maintaining relational exchanges that imply mutual gains with a long-term orientation. In this context, the breadth of the concept of Relationship Marketing is clear, which is not limited to just a customer loyalty program or database management, and therefore cannot be confused with its implementation tools - the Customer Relationship Management (CRM) and Database Management (DBM).

As prioritized by Salvador, Trés and Costalonga (2013), fundamentals such as long-term orientation, building emotional bonds with customers, trying to gain a deeper understanding of consumers and developing trust have been overlooked in the application of these tools. and commitment between the parties.

These distortions mischaracterize the foundation of Relationship Marketing, whose main focus, as D'Angelo, Schneider and Larán (2006) recall, is the creation of sustainable competitive advantages for organizations. The same authors point out that the establishment of true relationships, anchored in the principles of Relationship Marketing, on the other hand, is able to offer organizations this advantage.

For this, according to Salvador, Trés and Costalonga (2013), a combination of elements that addresses tangible and intangible aspects and that includes beliefs, values, knowledge, skills and diverse resources expressed in the business culture and in the strategic guidelines is essential. , whether formalized or not. In this way, the effective adoption of Relationship Marketing becomes possible, as a climate of commitment is created throughout the organizational environment, whose actions begin to converge towards the achievement of this purpose.

D'Angelo, Schneider and Larán (2006) conclude the reasoning by assuring that without culture and strategy - CRM, DBM, loyalty programs, among others, become activities committed to watertight actions and limited impact.

In this scenario, one can verify the pertinence of applying the concept of Relationship Marketing in the service sector which, according to Slongo and Müssnich (2005), is justified by the greater involvement of consumers with companies in this sector due to the basic characteristics of the service: relationship with customers, perishability, intangibility, inseparability and customization.

In order to manage these peculiarities, the relationship marketing approach is essential. In this way, Oliveira, Brito and Beker (2013), point out that relationship management is presented as the best way to deal with the intangibility of services, in addition to stating that any problems in providing the service are solved through the creation of links lasting relationships between suppliers and customers.

Jesus (2003), Madruga (2004), Mady (2009) among other authors point out that in the implementation of a service strategy, a Relationship Marketing approach and an excellent capacity for interactive marketing are essential. With these situations clarified, a technological tool responsible for the implementation of relationship marketing can be conceptualized: the CRM. According to Kotler and Keller (2008), CRM is about the careful management of accurate information about each customer and all points of contact with them, in order to maximize their loyalty.

According to Mady (2009), CRM comprises a combination of strategies based on Relationship Marketing, applied with the support of information and communication technologies. Almeida and Mello (2004), complement the reasoning, stating that the CRM should be viewed as the starting point for establishing customized strategies for different consumer profiles.

Almeida and Mello (2004) also point out that, based on the information produced and based on pre-existing service relationships, profiles of behavior and preference can be identified, grouping customers into virtual relationship communities. In addition to emphasizing that, generated from a database, micro-segmentation in communities facilitates the application of interactive commercial practices that fully satisfy the specific needs of consumers.

Kotler and Keller (2008), ensure such a position, stating that, thanks to the effective use of information about each account, the CRM enables companies to offer excellent customer

service in real time. In addition to emphasizing that, based on what they know about each of them, companies can customize their products, services, programs, messages and media. Having explained the Relationship Marketing approach, it is interesting to observe how companies have acted in the process of retaining their customers, in addition to verifying the understanding of the authors in this matter.

LOYALTY CONCEPTS

Loyalty is winning over customers, however, it requires companies to make similar efforts to keep them partners and loyal. There is no way to keep the customer effectively without loyalty. Only the loyalty strategy can lead to obtaining a long relationship, based on the intensification of loyalty relationships (PEDROSO, 2016).

In this way, wanting to build and maintain customer loyalty means that the company is not only interested in being able to sell at any cost: it is interested in obtaining long-term profitability, repeat purchases and customer retention. It is this loyalty that generates continuous income for the company (ZENONE, 2006).

Reflecting on values is essential for customer loyalty, emphasizing that it is necessary to offer a value proposition that is much better than that offered by the competition and not simply offering immediate benefits. This value must also be managed through quality management in the company (KURY, 2013).

Loyalty arises from Relationship Marketing and most of the time requires efforts to continue selling and pleasing your customers. A company needs to take several steps to implement the customer-oriented strategy (ZENONE, 2006).

Customer loyalty strategies

It is essential for the company to have a strategic thought on how to apply marketing actions with the objective of increasing productive results, through strategies linked to the correct use of marketing tools. The company needs to know who its customers are, in order to offer personalized products or services in order to make the experience of the customer's relationship with the brand unique, adding values and providing maximum interaction between both (LENZI, KIESEL and ZUCCO , 2010).

There are two essential ways to strengthen and absorb customers, they are, creating obstacles to avoid change and offering a high degree of customer satisfaction, thus preventing them from looking for a competing company to make their purchases (KOTLER 2000, 2003) .

Next, the main strategies that companies can adopt to better serve their customers and keep them loyal to the organization are presented by item.

a) Quality of service

Nowadays, the market is facing an economic and social reality, in which there is a multitude of organizations that manufacture the most varied products and service offerings. However, for a company to remain in a competitive market, it is essential to guarantee its space in the face of competitors, to win and retain customers, since when these customers have a close relationship with a brand of products or services, they disclose the same to their customers, relatives and friends (PEREIRA and BASTOS, 2009).

One of the most relevant points for a company to remain firm in the current and competitive market is the present customer with their purchasing power and loyalty (CHIAVENATO, 2007). Customer service is the final proof. Therefore, offering good treatment at the time of sale produces satisfaction for those who consume a lot. The company will hardly run the risk of losing its clientele , as long as its main focus is to serve its consumers with tranquility and agility (SALOMÃO, 2018).

However, it is essential to understand that quality service is not just about treatment or courtesy, but means adding benefits to products and services in order to exceed consumer expectations. And, in addition, offering a quality service allows the customer, in addition to returning to your company, to also refer their friends. The business organization can attract and conquer its customers, as it manages to overcome the competition from a better service and to satisfy their needs and expectations (KOTLER, 2000).

The way the customer is treated within the company makes all the difference, as quality service satisfies and wins over customers (PEDROSO, 2016). In this way, the organization that provides quality services and products to its customers already takes a step to survive in the current market. It is essential that the company listens to its customers and, therefore, finds possible solutions to improve customer satisfaction (GIANESI and CORRÊA, 2000).

b) Customer loyalty

To achieve loyalty, it is essential to know the customer, recognize their characteristics and identify their needs and desires. It is with this information that companies can gain trust from their clientele and consequently their loyalty (PINHEIRO, 2006).

The loyal customer is characterized by the way he buys, repeating his purchases regularly he will recommend the company to other people because he is immune to competitive pressure. It tolerates eventual failures in the service it receives due to the relationship established by a normally good service (GRIFFIN, 2001).

Given this, retaining loyal customers prevents them from starting to buy from the competition. A long-term relationship with the customer produces a degree of trust, respect and attention that makes it difficult for him to want the competition's product (GRIFFIN, 2001).

In this way, loyalty must be seen as a survival factor and must be an established commitment to the mission and culture of all companies. Priorities such as value, loyalty and satisfaction should be the basis of organizational concerns (MOUTELLA, 2004).

It is possible to argue that, in order to have loyal customers, it is essential that companies change their ideologies, change the expression, for example, completing a sale by starting a relationship and building loyalty, taking the economic side and focusing on relationship building (JESUS , 2003).

Loyalty strategies are extremely related to Relationship Marketing strategies. A loyal customer will automatically have a relationship with the brand he chooses to be loyal to. However, it should be noted that not all consumers develop a good relationship with service providers (WARD and DAGGER, 2007).

METHODOLOGY

This research is classified as descriptive with a focus on portraying the characteristics of the object of study, making an analysis without interfering with the collected data. The research has a qualitative approach due to the characteristics of descriptive investigation, which made it possible to identify the relevant elements to the research about their Relationship Marketing practices in their establishments (GIL, 2008).

As for the means, the study is of bibliographic competence which allows a deeper understanding of the subject in question, also fitting as a multiple case study, through an applied field research in a chain of drugstores in the city of Alagoinhas/ BA, enabling the analysis and comparison of cases, for the same phenomenon, inspired by studies by Minayo (1994).

The research subjects are the managers of this network of Pharmacies, for whom the semi-structured interview technique was applied, based on an open, pre-elaborated

questionnaire applied to the managers of each chosen drugstore or the person responsible for decision-making.

In this research, content analysis was applied. This procedure consists of a set of communication analysis techniques, based on collected data, aiming to identify what is being said about a given topic (BARDIN, 2006).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The pharmacy chain that participated in the present study has the mission of providing its customers with products and services with safety, agility and convenience for their well-being. Thus demonstrating, perfectly, the reason for its existence. Data collection was carried out through an interview with the network's commercial supervisor, who has worked for the company for more than 10 years.

Specific Marketing strategies are related to different activities associated with the components of the marketing mix, which are:

- a) Product - when the pharmacy receives new products to resell, it carries out actions in the stores to publicize these products and offers them to customers to see if there will be approval.

As for the packaging, some are made of recyclable material and come in different sizes, allowing customization according to the needs of the customers. They also bring the company's logo and its caps, a strategy designed as a way to differentiate its brand from other companies in the field.

- b) Distribution - the company has delivery of its products, and this home delivery is at an additional cost for customers.
- c) Promotion - one of the first measures to be taken was the organization and opening of a marketing department followed by the hiring of a marketing professional with specific training, becoming responsible for the company's image, with the expansion of the pharmacy the director noted that it was necessary to renew communication with the client, said the manager.

The marketing department was organized with the purpose of resuming communication and publicizing the units to old customers, who already had a connection with the brand (not only through their experiences but also through their parents and grandparents) and knew the quality of the products. products; and to introduce the brand to future consumers.

The department is responsible for the process of creating the communication concept, that is, organizing the ideas of what you want to pass on to the general public, up to the final execution and contracting of the supplier, which in this case are outsourced companies such as graphics and TV stations responsible for the reproduction of these contents.

It is also your responsibility to carry out marketing actions. The company has its own creative department in its marketing area. In the mid-2010s, the company's logo was updated, a joint action between the Marketing department and a contracted advertising company, where the entire brand design was renewed and there was follow-up by a consulting firm. In all actions that took place, including: implementation of the new logo, communication of changes to consumers, promotional vehicles used, uniforming of employees, etc.

- d) Price - the price is the big differential, as the drugs are cheaper than traditional drugs from large laboratories (on average 20% cheaper). The pharmacy renewed its operating system at the end of the 2010s, before using ENTERPRISE and now it is using OMIE, which is a system that offers the CRM, which brings all possible updates related to marketing, and is updating the registration of its customers, which is currently incomplete, with only the name and telephone number of these people.

This has made it difficult to carry out promotional actions directly with customers, and has also made it difficult to draw up some points in this research. They intend to complete it with other data such as CPF and e-mail, in order to be able to send promotional e-mails, congratulate you on your birthday and provide a special discount on the purchase of products.

The company sponsors events in the health area, that is, events that are organized by undergraduate or graduate courses in the areas of medicine, nutrition, pharmacy and aesthetics, among others, or that have these areas as a target audience. The strategy is a way of getting closer to possible future partners of the organization, the professionals, prescribers, who need to know and trust the brand in order to indicate it to their patients, in the words of the manager: “the professionals (prescribers) knowing that we do a serious job in the health area, they will recommend their patients so that they can buy their medicine with us. Not for a financial advantage, but for believing in our work”.

As another form of sponsorship, the pharmacy chain offers labor to develop projects in conjunction with specialized professionals. The research and development department associated with the Marketing department produces technical and specialized content for health professionals, carrying out studies on new substances that are coming to the market and different treatments, forming an educational partnership.

The internal communication of the company is the responsibility of the Marketing and HR sectors. It brings in its internal communication system the division into three categories of what must be done in the organization to facilitate internal communication, they are:

- Institutional Internal Communication – each new employee undergoes general training, called introductory. It lasts a whole day and includes the presentation of the company's history, organizational concepts, expected employee behavior, mission and vision, and also includes a moment of integration; and the specific training of each area depends on the position that will be occupied by him.
- Internal Communication Vehicles – the pharmacy has two official communication channels, which are: internal bulletin board in each sector, and a general one for each store with notices about training, birthdays of the month and other relevant notices and the internal corporate email; there are also corporate cell phones for more urgent communication. The supply of these channels is the responsibility of the marketing sector. Communication is very efficient, always being two-way, where employees are free to talk at any time with their superiors, taking criticisms, suggestions and doubts.
- Relationship actions – training programs are implemented for managers, through workshops and training, with the aim of spreading the culture of communication and multiplying concepts, expanding the scope and disseminating, beyond the area of communication, the way in which the company exchanges its information, generating and sharing knowledge.

Social responsibility can lead companies to perform actions that cause impacts both inside and outside the company. Focusing on improvements in the quality of life of its employees, the company has an internal program in which, once a week, a professional performs a work workout with everyone, visiting one sector at a time, seeking to adjust the posture and disposition of the employees who sometimes exercise activities with repetitive movements.

As for the actions that can impact the quality of life of society, analyzing the ethical and legal aspect, the company follows all the standards and norms required by ANVISA both in the acquisition and disposal of material, where ANVISA itself makes periodic visits to inspect and certifying the company. Analyzing the aspect of the environment and conscious consumption, most of the packages produced by the pharmacy are recyclable and have different sizes to meet the needs of customers, thus avoiding wasting medicine.

Since people in Brazil are increasingly using the internet to research products and services, the company has been investing in the use of social networks (own website, Facebook, Instagram and WhatsApp) as a means of exposing its products, communicating its brand and establish a direct communication channel with your customers. The marketing sector is responsible for managing all social networks.

The website was updated in 2018, both aesthetically and in terms of content, and presents a bit of the history of the pharmacy, the products that are sold, address and contact telephone number. Facebook is the most used social network by the pharmacy. All content is posted by the Marketing team, but receives collaboration from other sectors of the organization.

Its posts are divided into: health tips (content written by pharmacists), recruitment portal (job opportunities that arise in the pharmacy are shown) and informative (talking about products, promotions that are being carried out). The page also has a topic where customers can rate the pharmacy by leaving positive or negative comments. Instagram is used as an extension of the Facebook page, where the contents that appear there are reproduced. As a way to streamline customer communication with the company, along with Instagram and Facebook, the most used tool is WhatsApp.

With just one week of use, more than 80 people had already requested the service, ordering products, clarifying doubts, giving suggestions. The telemarketing team (the same one that takes care of the customer relationship center) is responsible for this channel, which appears as a means of approaching the younger public (public that the pharmacy is trying to conquer) and to reduce the distance between the customer and the company. Due to the good acceptance of this new communication tool, the company already aims to add one more employee to its relationship center.

FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

It can be seen that companies have been investing in marketing as a way to promote and differentiate their products, strengthening relationships and building ties with their customers. For this, it uses the correct management of its brands, through some strategies that can be grouped into different categories, namely: specific marketing strategies, holding events and sponsorships, internal communication and organizational culture, social responsibility and use of the internet and networks social.

This case study achieved its objectives, which were to identify the strategies used by the Pharmacy network to strengthen its brand, understand the reasons that led the company to use them and evaluate the results of implementing these strategies.

Due to the increase in competition and the displacement of the commercial center of the city where it operates (the commerce that was previously concentrated only in one neighborhood has expanded to others), the company felt the need to expand and strengthen its brand already known by customers, starting thus the physical expansion with the opening of some stores in different neighborhoods, since there was a demand there that was not met, and an excellent opportunity for growth.

Among the strategies used, the one that stood out the most and brought a more significant result was the use of social networks. The company was able to create a direct relationship channel with its customers, through which there is efficient communication and it is possible to collect important information about the needs and satisfaction of consumers.

It was found that the organization has been efficiently applying Marketing strategies, obtaining satisfactory results and managing to consolidate its brand. A point to be thought about is its objective of reaching the younger public, one option would be to carry out surveys and apply questionnaires together with the analysis of their results to understand how this portion of the population sees pharmacies and what strategies are necessary. to make them loyal.

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